

NUMERICAL STUDY OF COMPACTION INFLUENCE ON SPRING-IN OF THIN COMPOSITE COMPONENTS MANUFACTURED BY VACUUM BAG PROCESS

L. Sorrentino and C. Bellini*

Department of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, University of Cassino and Southern Lazio, Cassino, Italy

*Corresponding author (c.bellini@unicas.it)

Keywords: *cure process, thin composite component, compaction, spring-in, vacuum bag, prepreg.*

1. Introduction

During the manufacturing process of polymer matrix composite materials, geometric unconformities may arise due to the onset of residual stresses, that are mostly generated by two factors: 1) the chemical shrinkage of the matrix, due to polymerization process; 2) the difference in value between the CTE of the matrix and that of the fibres during cooling [1, 2]. In the production of simple geometry parts, such as flat laminates with symmetrical and balanced stratification, these phenomena do not give rise to particular problems of compliance, because such stresses are automatically balanced thanks to stacking sequence. The behaviour of thin non-planar form laminates (L, T, U) is not the same as the former ones: the condition of stresses and deformations is more complex and causes geometric differences [3, 4], even if the laminate presents a symmetrical and balanced stacking sequence. For example, “spring-in” is a phenomenon caused by residual stresses due to resin shrinkage during the cure process of a L-shaped component. Spring-in is a distortion in shape visible through a change in angle, as denoted in Fig. 1.

Another problem is the thickness reduction of the laminate, due to resin squeeze. This phenomenon is very important for vacuum bag process, in fact resin flows away from the fibres for the application of pressure, and the pressure field could be uneven, depending on the geometry. Consequently the thickness reduction is not uniform and it depends on the pressure that is applied during the production cycle and on geometry features [5, 6].

The amount of resin inside the component, and its variation during processing, influences the onset of residual stresses, in fact these latter depend on changes that happen in the matrix. Therefore resin flow and compaction behaviour during cure process have a significant effect on final thickness profile, residual stress distribution and distortion of composite structures.

In common practice spring-in and compaction are considered as totally distinct phenomena, so in the past models for only spring-in or for only compaction were developed [6, 8]. In the present work a new approach to take in account both problems is settled, in fact a new kind of analysis to take in account both residual stresses and compaction that take place during cure is developed. The performed analysis is composed by two different steps, as denoted in Fig. 2. In the former, a 2-D finite element model is implemented in order to predict the compaction and the thickness reduction of L-shaped structures. In the latter, a thermo-chemical-mechanical model is realized to determine the curing state and the residual stress condition at the end of the curing process. So a combined model of compacting and curing processes with a double analysis is presented, in order to discover the influence of compaction on spring-in angle. A schematic representation is reported in Fig. 3. Finally, the relationships between the different degree of compaction and the corresponding value of spring-in are studied, and from the result it can be seen that a higher value of thickness reduction will produce the smallest residual stresses for the L-shaped composite structures.

Fig. 1. Spring-in on L-shaped component.

Fig. 2. Fem simulation of vacuum bag process: a) compaction, b) spring-in.

Fig. 3. Method for a combined model of compaction and residual stress.

2. Background

The composite material presents residual stresses that arise during the cure cycle, and they cause distortions of the component, affecting the compliance with geometric and dimensional tolerances. In general, the development of distortions in a laminate is due to more combined actions, among them [9]:

- Material anisotropy;
- Material inhomogeneity;
- Thermal field inhomogeneity;
- Different CTE for mould and component;
- Heat that rises from polymerization process, that is exothermic.

In the angular profiles the different CTEs of the materials play a leading role. For thin laminates the ratio between radius of curvature and thickness becomes a sensitive parameter if it is above 10. The elastic return generated by the residual stresses in the L-shaped laminates is known by the term spring-in (also called springback or springforward) and it is the difference between the value of the theoretical (Φ_1) and the measured value once the part is extracted from the mould (Φ_2).

$$\Delta\Phi = \Phi_1 - \Phi_2 \quad (1)$$

The spring-in is reduced [10]:

- increasing the number of layers in the laminate;
- increasing the angle of the profile (for example from 60° to 135°);
- arranging plies orthogonally according to the sequence (0/90). This configuration determines an elastic return particularly reduced compared to laminates with layers arranged with inclination of the fibres at 45° .

As concerns the effects of curing parameters on the thickness of flat laminates, the experimental results indicate that to obtain an improved dimensional stability the first temperature dwell must end before the gel point and the autoclave pressure should be applied 15°C before the gel point [11].

The studies carried out on unidirectional laminates indicate that the CTE difference determines tensile residual stresses along the direction perpendicular to the fibres and compression ones along the fibres direction [12]. Interlaminar stresses must be considered in the case of multilayer laminates. The proposed analytical model evaluates the development of both normal and shear residual stresses and it shows that, in a symmetric laminate, the interface tensions increase away from the centre of the laminate.

The evolution of residual stresses was monitored by several authors, who carried out some studies interrupting the curing and measuring the deformation of the laminate [13]. It was found that

initially compressive stresses arise due to increasing temperature, then, during the polymerization, chemical shrinkage causes tension stresses. Most of residual stresses rises during the cooling phase (more than 50%), that make the laminate bend when it is demoulded.

Other works show through analytical and experimental models that the portion of the residual stresses developed during polymerization is due to chemical shrinkage and to the change of the elastic properties. These phenomena make stresses rise in the matrix that cause the laminate bending: this curvature is equal to 1.5% of the laminate thickness. It is also demonstrated that for multilayer 0/90 laminates, thicker than 10 mm, residual stresses are negative in the middle of the laminate, while they are positive in the surface. This distribution is due to the development of inside - outside curing, i.e. the progress of the reaction at the centre is greater than that in the external areas. In this case when the resin in the outer layers cures and tends to shrink, it is hindered by the material in the core which is already polymerized. The immediate consequence is a state of tensile stress in the outer zones, compression in the inner ones.

Another important cause of geometric-dimensional unconformities is the compaction due to the resin flow which occurs in the first part of the curing process, when the resin viscosity decreases. In curved laminates a non-uniform thickness reduction can be observed, in particular in the curve zone there is a poor compaction with formation of voids and distortions.

Residual deformation or warpage are influenced by residual stresses development during the cure, the calculation of which requires the knowledge of local elastic properties that are functions of local volume fraction of fibres. This last depends on the resin flow, which can be separated into two mechanisms: the filtration flow and shear flow. As regards filtration flow, applying a pressure to the laminate a phenomenon takes place similar to the squeezing of a sponge and that causes the leakage of resin. In this case, the resin flows along the fibres and the flow must be coupled with the compaction behaviour of the fibres layer to obtain the final thickness of the laminate. For the shear flow, the composite behaves as a very viscous fluid filled with inextensible fibres. The filtration flow is typically used to model the compaction of a thermosetting matrix composite, while the shear flow is applied to thermoplastic matrix composites.

3. Fem modelling

As concerns the simulation of manufacturing processes for composite materials, various phenomena that take place during cure process are to be considered, as thermal flows, fluid behaviour of resin and cure kinetics that are the causes of the microscopic and macroscopic defects [14]. In particular there are two dominant events that occur during the autoclave forming of prepreg materials subjected to pressure and temperature: compaction and cure.

The former takes place during the initial phase of process and it can be modelled as a viscous resin flow through a porous medium formed by the fibres. Resin pressure field is very important during this stage since it determines some defects such as inhomogeneity of resin distribution.

Cure process can be modelled by thermo-mechanical analysis, regarding cure and residual stresses. In this phase, heat and cure influence deformations and tensions, therefore the knowledge of parameters and models is very important.

The typical approach for these multi-physical simulations is a step by step one, simulating any type of physics within each increment.

3.1. Compaction model

Compaction is a very important step that occurs in the first part of the cure cycle, when resin viscosity is low, in fact a resin flow is established through the fibrous layers of reinforcement and the resin is ejected, resulting in a different reduction thickness for components having a L or T form, since the pressure field exerted by vacuum bag is uneven.

This cycle phase can be simulated using models typical of the study on soil compaction, considering the resin as the fluid and the fibres as the porous medium. Actually they have many limitations since they consider isotropic some material properties, and this is not correct for composite materials, that are strongly anisotropic.

Cam-Clay Model is often used to describe the properties of non-elastic behaviour materials as soil. The parameters required for finite element implementation are: the compression index λ , the recompression index κ and the slope of the critical state line M . These parameters are normally obtained through laboratory tests, but these tests lose their validity when applied to composite materials. Therefore a procedure for determining these parameters was developed, correlating them to the index of compressibility (C_c) and to the index of swelling (C_s), which are connected to the viscosity

properties of resin. Preliminary analyses of a plain laminate compaction were required to obtain the values of C_c .

3.2. Curing model

To accurately calculate the non-linear cure term, an iterative scheme between each step of cure and temperature calculation is used. The starting point is the determination of cure field for a single step. Then, the heat flow generated by the exothermic curing process is calculated and transferred to the thermal step. Once both cure and heat steps are terminated, the degree of cure and the temperatures are transferred to the mechanical step. By means of the shrinkage models, the deformation due to the shrinkage are calculated and, consequently, the residual stresses are accurately determined.

As regards the analysis, the thermal one is based on the energy balance of the system, according to [15]:

$$\rho_c c_{p,c} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla(k_c \nabla T) + \rho_r V_r \dot{Q} \quad (2)$$

in which ρ represents material density, c_p is the specific heat, t is the time, T is the temperature, k is the thermal conductivity coefficient of the composite material, that is anisotropic, \dot{Q} is heat generation rate by chemical reaction, V is the volumetric percentage. The subscript c and r refer respectively to composite and matrix properties, while f stands for fibre reinforcement. The in-plane thermal conductivity is calculated by a weighted average on volumetric fraction, while the through thickness one according to Springer-Tsai model:

$$k_t = \left[\left(1 - V_f^{0.5}\right) + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{V_f^{0.5}} + \frac{B}{2}} \right] * k_r \quad (3)$$

Composite density can be derived from volumetric fraction of fibres and matrix through the rule of mixture [16, 17], while specific heat can be computed as

$$c_{p,c} = (V_r \rho_r c_{p,r} + V_f \rho_f c_{p,f}) / \rho_c \quad (4)$$

In order to determinate the heat generation rate it must be considered that it depends on the total heat of reaction H_r and on the cure rate ($d\alpha/dt$):

$$\dot{Q} = \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) H_r \quad (5)$$

The cure rate can be expressed as [18, 19]

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K(T) \cdot f(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

The first term of the product can be calculated as

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (7)$$

in which n and m are reaction orders, while the function $K(T)$ in equation (6) can be determined with an Arrhenius relation:

$$K = A_c \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) \quad (8)$$

in which E is activation energy, R is the universal gas constant and A_c is frequency factor. All the constants in these models can be determined through laboratory tests, such as differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [20].

As concerns the mechanical analysis, it is a 2D plain strain one, in which the contact between composite material and aluminium is "glue" and the loads are due to the pressure applied by vacuum bag, to the thermal expansion and shrinkage (described through CTE) and to chemical shrinkage, that can be defined as [21]:

$$\begin{aligned} V_r^S &= 0.0 & \alpha < \alpha_{C1} \\ V_r^S &= A * \alpha_S + (V_r^{S\infty} - A) * \alpha_S^2 \\ & \text{for } \alpha_{C1} \leq \alpha \leq \alpha_{C2} \\ V_r^S &= V_r^{S\infty} & \text{for } \alpha \geq \alpha_{C2} \\ \alpha_S &= \frac{\alpha - \alpha_{C1}}{\alpha_{C2} - \alpha_{C1}} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In which α_{C1} is the critical degree of cure after which the resin shrinkage begins, α_{C2} is the critical degree of cure after which the resin shrinkage stops, α_S is the degree of cure shrinkage, V_r^S is the resin volumetric cure shrinkage and A is a linear cure shrinkage coefficient.

4. Finite element modelling: analysis and results

In the present work the influence of compaction on an L-shaped profile was studied, whose initial dimensions are shown in Fig. 4, realized by means of vacuum bag technology on a convex mould placed at the laminate intrados.

The most critical point of the process modelling is the difficulty to obtain some physical characteristics of the material, which constitute the inputs to the model, due to the excessive number of tests required and to the complexity of them. In fact some phenomena occur during the process, whose simulation requires the knowledge of many properties, as seen in the previous paragraph. It must also be considered that this characterization is often required for a temperature range $20^{\circ}\text{C} \div 180^{\circ}\text{C}$, moreover it must be made in function of the degree of cure (from $\alpha=0$ to $\alpha=1$) and of the fibres volumetric percentage V_f . Finally, the composite laminates have an anisotropic behaviour, in fact they are approximately transversely isotropic or orthotropic. Even for the simplest of these cases, two constants are required to describe the conductivity, the thermal expansion and deformation due to shrinkage and five constants for the mechanical behaviour.

The component was made of 8 layers of HX42, a carbon and epoxy resin prepreg, whose properties are shown in Tab. 1. The mould is formed by a steel Fe360 tube of square section reinforced with wood to ensure greater rigidity.

To achieve the aim of this work three cases were studied, reported in Tab. 2: the effects due to a different compaction in function of the absolute pressure applied and of the use of a perforated release agent were analysed.

Fig. 4. Component dimension [mm].

Property	Value
Density [kg/m^3]	$\rho_r = 1250$; $\rho_f = 1800$
Specific heat [J/kgK]	$C_{pr} = 1260$; $C_{pf} = 712$
Thermal conductivity [W/mK]	$k_r = 0.24$; $k_f = 2.51$
Young's moduli [Pa]	$E_{11} = E_{22} = 6.05 * 10^{10}$; $E_{33} = 4 * 10^9$
Poisson's moduli	$\nu_{12} = 0.3$; $\nu_{31} = 0.0165$; $\nu_{23} = 0.25$
Shear moduli [Pa]	$G_{12} = 2.32692 * 10^{10}$; $G_{31} = G_{23} = 1.6 * 10^9$;
Total cure shrinkage	0.0487
Activation energy [J/mol]	79858.48
Pre-exponential factor [s^{-1}]	$1.08 * 10^9$
m	0.890304
n	0.812198
Reaction heat [J/Kg]	248452.1

Tab. 1. Physical properties of HX42.

Test	Absolute Pressure	Release film
A*	0.03 MPa	Non perforated
B	0.03 MPa	Perforated
C	0.10 MPa	Perforated

Tab. 2. Test condition (*only A test has been verified experimentally).

A 2D mesh was realized, due to component geometry and to load conditions, to use less computational resources. This mesh, shown in Fig. 5, is constituted by quad plain strain elements, and it concerns only half geometry, as geometrical and loads symmetries were exploited. Furthermore, for the simulation of the real heat flow, the breather effect was introduced.

Fig. 5. Fem model for the process simulation of L-shaped component.

The model used to simulate process schedules a former analysis of compaction in which the component, considered constituted by soil material type, undergoes preform compaction in a single step. So thickness reduction due to resin flow through fibres is simulated. The displacements and the stresses resulting from this analysis are then inserted as initial condition for the subsequent thermo-structural analysis, concerning the cure process, in which the material is treated as a composite, simulating the temperature and pressure cycle with the relative effects of shrinkage and spring-in. Thickness values on two significant points were obtained from numerical analyses (Fig. 6): the flat part at $L/2$ distance from the specimen extremity and the curved part.

Fig. 6. Measurement point for thickness evaluation

Fig. 7 shows the results obtained for compaction. The final thickness comparison between case A and case B demonstrate that the use of a perforated release film (case B) results in a greater thickness reduction, and therefore in a greater laminate compaction. Moreover, the comparison between case B and case C reveals that a greater pressure applied during the cure cycle (case C) determines a

more uniform thickness of laminate, as well as a greater compaction.

As concerns the spring-in, the results obtained by the numerical analysis for the three cases of study are shown in Fig. 8 and they demonstrate that the value of the spring-in decreases as the degree of compaction increases. This is due to the fact that the amount of resin decreases with increasing compaction, while the fibres quantity remains constant: since only the resin undergoes the shrinkage, the lower its quantity is the weaker its effects are.

Results obtained from numerical simulation are denoted in Tab. 3.

Fig. 7. Final thickness comparison.

Fig. 8. Spring-in comparison.

Specimen	Final Thickness [mm]		Spring-in [degree]
	Flat	Corner	
A	5.69	6.14	1.74
B	5.58	6.12	1.61
C	5.49	5.76	1.31

Tab. 3. Result obtained from numerical tests.

Preliminary experimental test were carried out under the same conditions of A case to check the validity of the FEM model, as visible in Fig. 9. Five specimens were tested.

The phases of the manufacturing cycle are those typical of a vacuum bag process:

- Bag and mould preparation;
- Prepreg cutting;
- Layering;
- Bag sealing;
- Polymerization.

Fig. 9. L-shaped component manufacturing.

Once the cure cycle was ended, the laminate was extracted and the final thickness and the spring-in were evaluated. The thickness was measured in correspondence of the flat part and the curved part, using a micrometer, with a resolution of 0.01 mm, whereas the spring-in was measured through a coordinate measuring machine.

The results regarding the thickness reduction are shown in Fig. 10. It can be noted that the experimental results, with a standard deviation of 0.3 mm, agree quite well with those obtained numerically. Moreover the compaction in the curved zone is lower than that in the flat zone as it was found from the thickness measurements along the specimen.

The results concerning the spring-in are shown in Fig. 11. It can be noted that the experimental results, with a standard deviation of 0.17°, well agree with the numerical ones.

Fig. 10. Result comparison between numerical simulation and experimental test for thickness reduction.

Fig. 11. Result comparison between numerical simulation and experimental test for spring-in angle.

5. Conclusion

In the present work, attention was paid to the thickness reduction and on its influence on the spring-in. The thickness reduction is the result of the preform compaction due to the resin flow through the fibrous layer, while the elastic return of the angle is generated by residual stresses caused by resin shrinkage. Simulation models have been developed for the two phenomena and they have been closely integrated together, to provide the unconformities at the end of cure process.

In fact compaction and cure are usually considered as separate phenomena, while in this work they were correlated. So a combined analysis of compaction and cure has been proposed. It is composed by a first step in which thickness reduction is simulated, through a structural-diffusion analysis, followed by a thermal-structural analysis which simulates the cure cycle and the associated phenomena such as resin shrinkage and spring-in. From the first analysis it is evident that the spring-in of the L-shaped laminates is inversely proportional to the thickness reduction of the same. This is due to the lower resin content and so to a reduced phenomenon of shrinkage, that is the consequence of a better compaction. Three

cases with increasing degree of compaction were numerically analysed according to this methodology, in function of the pressure applied and the type of release film used. The use of a perforated release film, with the same pressure level (case A → case B), has allowed a thickness reduction of 0.3% for corner zone and 1.9% for flat zone and a reduction of 7.4% for spring-in, while a pressure increase of 70 kPa with the same perforated release film (case B → case C) has caused a further thickness reduction of 1.6% for flat zone and 5.8% for corner zone and a decrease of 18.6% for spring-in. Some of these results were experimentally verified, and it was noticed that the error is included within the standard deviation obtained.

6. Acknowledgements

This work was carried out with the funding of the Italian M.I.U.R. (Ministry of Instruction, University and Technological Research). The authors wish to thank “Tecnologie Avanzate s.r.l.” and Eng. R. Aricò for their support in this work and their availability. Special thanks to Martina & Lorenzo S.

7. References

- [1] Chensong Dong “Process-induced deformation of composite T-stiffener structures”. *Composite Structures*, Vol. 92, pp. 1614-1619, 2010.
- [2] J. Magnus Svanberg, J. Anders Holmberg “Prediction of shape distortions Part I. FE-implementation of a path dependent constitutive model”. *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 35, pp. 711-721, 2004.
- [3] A. Johnston, R. Vaziri, and A. Poursartip “A plane strain model for process-induced deformation of laminated composite structures”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 35, No. 16, pp. 1435-1469, 2001.
- [4] M.R. Wisnom, M. Gigliotti, N. Ersoy, M. Campbell, K.D. Potter “Mechanisms generating residual stresses and distortion during manufacture of polymer–matrix composite structures”. *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 37, pp. 522-529, 2006.
- [5] V.A.F. Costa, A.C.M. Sousa “Modeling of flow and thermo-kinetics during the cure of thick laminated composites”. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, Vol. 42, pp. 15-22, 2003.
- [6] P. Hubert, “Aspects of flow and compaction of laminated composite shapes during cure”. *Ph.D. Thesis*, The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, 1996.
- [7] S.J. Lord, L.G. Stringer “A modelling approach for predicting residual stresses and distortions in polymer composites”. *Proceedings of ICCM 17, 17th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Edinburgh, UK, 27-31 July 2009.
- [8] T. Garstka, G. Cole, D. Irving, P. Lyons “Integrated finite element environment for composite process simulation”. *Proceedings of ICCM 17, 17th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Edinburgh, UK, 27-31 July 2009.
- [9] R. Akkerman, H.W. Wiersma, L.J.B. Peeters “Spring-forward in continuous fibre reinforced thermosets”. *University of Twente*, the Netherlands, 1998.
- [10] Tsang Luh Yang, Shih Ming Chen, Jong Pyng Chen “Spring back of composite laminate during cure”. *International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, 37th*, Anaheim, CA, Mar. 9-12, 1992, Proceedings (A93-15726 04-23), pp. 213-223.
- [11] Chen et al. “Dimensional stability of C/E composite laminate cured with autoclave”. *International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, 37th*, Anaheim, CA, Mar. 9-12, 1992, Proceedings (A93-15726 04-23), pp. 462-474.
- [12] Yiwang Bao, Shengbiao Su “An uneven strain model for analysis of residual stress and interface stress in laminate composites”. *Journal of composite materials*, Vol. 36, pp.1769-1778, 2002.
- [13] Q. Zhu, P. H. Geubelle “Dimensional accuracy of thermoset composites: shape optimization”. *Journal of composite materials*, 26 (5), pp.626-660, 1992.
- [14] S. Choudhry, S. Padmanaban, S.P. Wang, P. Nordlund, C. Bruzzo, M. Calcagni “Simulation of composite manufacturing with MSC products”. *MSC software corporation*, 2002.
- [15] L. Sorrentino, C. Bellini, L. Carrino, A. Leone, E. Mostarda, L. Tersigni “Cure process design to manufacture composite components with variable thickness by a closed die technology”. *Proceedings of ICCM 17, 17th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Edinburgh, UK, 27-31 July 2009.
- [16] Blest D. C., Duffy B. R., McKee S., Zulkifle A. K. “Curing simulation of thermoset composites”. *Composites: Part A*, 30, pp. 1289-1309, 1999.
- [17] Park H. C., Goo N. S., Min K. J., Yoon K. J. “Three-dimensional cure simulation of composite structures by finite element method”, *Composites Structures*, 62, pp. 51-57, 2003.
- [18] Teplinsky S. , Gutman E.M. “Computer simulation of process induced stress and strain during cure of thick-section thermosetting composites”. *Computational Material Science*, 6, pp. 71-76, 1996.
- [19] Joshi S. C., Lam Y.C. “Integrated approach for modelling cure and crystallization kinetics of different polymers in 3D pultrusion simulation”. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 174, pp. 178–182, 2006.
- [20] Shin D. D., Hanh H. T. “A consistent cure kinetic model for AS4/2502 graphite/epoxy”. *Composites: Part A*, 31, pp. 991-999, 2000.

- [21] Bogetti, T. A., Gillespie, J. W. "Process-Induced Stress and Deformation in Thick Section thermoset Composite Laminates", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 26, 626-660, 1992.